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Title: Crosstalk between mitochondria-ER contact sites and the apoptotic machinery as a novel health meter

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22 **Crosstalk between Mitochondria-ER contact sites and apoptotic machinery as**
23 **a novel health-meter**

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33

34 **Keywords:** MERCS, MAMs, Apoptosis, Inflammation, Neurodegeneration, cancer.

35

36 **Abstract**

37 Mitochondria-ER Contact Sites (MERCS) function as transient signalling platforms that
38 regulate essential cellular functions. MERCS are enriched in specific proteins and
39 lipids that connect mitochondria and the ER together, modulating their activities.
40 Dysregulation of MERCS is associated with several human pathologies, including
41 Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease and cancer. BCL-2 family proteins can
42 locate at MERCS and control essential cellular functions such as calcium signalling
43 and autophagy in addition to their role in mitochondrial apoptosis. Moreover, the BCL-
44 2-mediated apoptotic machinery was recently found to trigger cGAS/STING pathway
45 activation and proinflammatory response, a recognized hallmark in these diseases that
46 requires mitochondria-ER interplay. This Opinion article underscores the pivotal role of
47 MERCS in regulating essential cellular functions, focusing on their crosstalk with BCL-
48 2 family proteins and discusses how their dysregulation is linked to disease.

49

50 **MERCS, fundamental dynamic structures required for cellular homeostasis**

51 The interface between cellular organelles is increasingly recognized as a pivotal
52 platform governing essential biological processes in eukaryotic cells. Specifically, the
53 contact sites between mitochondria outer membrane (MOM) and the endoplasmic
54 reticulum (ER), referred to as Mitochondria-Endoplasmic Reticulum Contact Sites
55 (**MERCS**) also known as mitochondria-associated ER membranes (MAMs), represent
56 mostly transient dynamic modules enriched in specific lipids and specialized proteins
57 that define their structure and functions (*see Glossary*) [1,2]. These ER-mitochondrial
58 junctions, where the interorganellar distance ranges between 10 and 80 nm, serve as
59 key locations for **calcium (Ca²⁺) signalling**, lipid transfer, and play crucial roles in

60 cellular bioenergetics, proteostasis, **mitochondrial quality control**, **autophagy** and
61 **apoptotic cell death** [3,4].

62 Research employing techniques such as live-cell fluorescence and electron
63 microscopy has revealed several features of these tightly tethered, yet separate,
64 membrane structures. It is becoming clear that the number of contacts, the surface
65 area of contact and the interorganellar distance are three fundamental aspects of
66 MERCS mediated signalling affecting its triggering, amplification and kinetics [4,5].
67 Since both the ER and mitochondria are dynamic organelles, it is unclear how these
68 contact areas are established. In yeast, MERCS are maintained through a complex of
69 known composition called ER-mitochondria encounter structure, **ERMES** [6]. However,
70 in mammals the molecular architecture of MERCS formation and stabilization is more
71 intricate and poorly understood [7]. A handful of proteins have been described to
72 maintain MERCS, acting like membrane-tethers, including inositol 1,4,5-triphosphate
73 receptors (IP3Rs) [8] together with VDACs (Voltage dependent anion channels) [9];
74 the vesicle-associated membrane protein B (VAPB) associated to PTPIP51 (protein
75 tyrosine phosphatase-interacting protein-51) [10], mitofusin-2 (MFN2) and related
76 isoforms [11,12], B-cell receptor-associated protein-31 (BAP-31) [13] and PDZ
77 domain-containing protein 8 (PDZD8) [14] (**Figure 1**).

78 Each of these **MERCS-tethers** exhibit distinct characteristics and are intricately linked
79 to specific cellular functions and regulated by adaptors expressed in response to
80 diverse stimuli. Importantly, the proteins within these contact sites are neither exclusive
81 nor specific to MERCS, which presents technical challenges for understanding their
82 exact nature. Moreover, within a single MERCS, multiple specialized interaction
83 domains may coexist, further underscoring their dynamic nature being able to remodel
84 in response to changes in the environment and meet the metabolic needs of the cell
85 [15]. For example, IP3Rs are key mediators of ER-mitochondria Ca^{2+} homeostasis,
86 acting as channels for Ca^{2+} transport. IP3R forms a tetrameric complex with VDAC,
87 the molecular chaperone GRP75 (Glucose-regulated protein 75) and the deglycase
88 DJ-1, to modulate the Ca^{2+} transfer from the ER to the mitochondrial matrix, using the
89 mitochondrial calcium uniporter (MCU) [16–18], which can result in stimulation of Krebs
90 cycle enzymes and OxPhos [19,20]. The VAPB-PTPIP51 tether complex is related to
91 Ca^{2+} signalling as well, but also to alterations in mitochondrial morphology and
92 aggregation [10,21]. Depletion of either VAPB or PTPIP51 leads to the disruption of
93 MERCS, perturbation of Ca^{2+} transport and autophagy stimulation [10,22]. Some
94 authors also reported that MFN2 and its splicing variants can act as a physical tether
95 stabilizing the contact between both organelles, favouring lipid transfer and regulating
96 mitochondrial dynamics [11,12]. However, this remains a contentious topic within the
97 field [23–26]. Finally, BAP-31 has been shown to modulate mitochondrial oxygen
98 consumption, autophagy and apoptotic cell death [13]. These studies collectively
99 reveal that MERCS-tethers have distinct roles in regulating specific cellular processes.
100 While their investigation is technically demanding, it is crucial for uncovering their vital
101 contributions to maintaining cellular homeostasis.

102 These diverse MERCS-mediated functions are known to be dysregulated in multiple
103 human pathologies including cancer and neurodegenerative diseases such as
104 Alzheimer's disease (AD) and Parkinson's disease (PD) [3,27–29]. Interestingly, recent
105 evidence unravelled that MERCS are altered during cellular **senescence**, which could

106 mediate their impact on aging and age-related diseases [30]. However, the driving
107 cellular mechanisms behind these roles remain poorly defined. Proteins belonging to
108 the **BCL-2 family**, which are considered the main regulators of mitochondrial apoptosis
109 [31–34], are key regulators of MERCS-associated functions and strongly contribute to
110 the cell death imbalance observed in these age-related diseases. In this Opinion
111 article, we will discuss the role of MERCS in health and disease, with a novel
112 perspective emphasizing the crosstalk between MERCS and the BCL-2 mediated
113 apoptotic machinery, regulating cell death and inflammation, and highlighting non-
114 apoptotic BCL-2 roles in cellular homeostasis.

115

116 **BCL-2 and MERCS, a novel cellular health-meter?**

117 BCL-2 family proteins form a complex interaction network in which mitochondrial and
118 ER membranes play a key modulatory role. These proteins are typically classified into
119 three main groups: i) the anti-apoptotics (e.g. BCL-2, BCL-XL, or MCL1), also known
120 as guardians, that prevent MOM permeabilization (MOMP) and consequently
121 apoptosis; ii) the proapoptotic multidomain or effectors (e.g. BAX and BAK), which
122 directly induce MOMP and apoptosis by forming a pore at the mitochondria; and iii) the
123 BH3-only proteins (e.g. BIM, BID or BAD), which trigger apoptosis by either blocking
124 anti-apoptotics or directly activating effectors [35–38].

125 During apoptosis, BAX and BAK converge at the mitochondria to form the apoptotic
126 pore, inducing MOMP and the subsequent release of pro-apoptogenic factors to the
127 cytosol [36]. The tunable protein:lipid nature of the formed pores, allows the passage
128 of small molecules such as cytochrome c or SMAC, but also larger molecules, such as
129 mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) [39–42]. Once in the cytosol, released cytochrome c and
130 SMAC promote the assembly of the apoptosome, inducing caspase activation and
131 apoptotic cell death (**Figure 2**). Importantly, sublethal activation of this machinery, with
132 only partial release of the mitochondrial content, a phenomenon that is known as
133 **minority MOMP**, is associated with a sublethal caspase activation, damage in the
134 nuclear DNA and genomic instability [43]. Released mtDNA in the cytosol, is
135 recognised by nucleic acid sensors like cGAS (cytosolic cyclic GMP–AMP synthase).
136 cGAS activation leads to the synthesis of 2'3' cyclic GMP–AMP (cGAMP), which
137 activates the ER-localized Stimulator of interferon genes (STING). Activated, STING
138 translocates to the Golgi, inducing TANK-binding kinase 1 (TBK1) and Interferon
139 regulatory factor 3 (IRF3) phosphorylation, inducing the expression of type I interferons
140 [44–46].

141 Of note, this pro-inflammatory response is initiated within the mitochondria but relies
142 on the ER for its amplification, underscoring the role of MERCS (**Figure 2**). In this
143 regard, knock down of the MERCS tether VAPB substantially decreases interferon-
144 mediated inflammation [47] and STING depletion potentiates VDAC2/GRP75-
145 mediated MERCS formation impairing mitochondrial function [48]. Indeed,
146 mitochondrial VDAC2 was recently identified as a new STING binding partner able to
147 regulate BAX/BAK apoptotic activities [48–50]. This highlights the importance of the
148 crosstalk between MERCS-tethers, BCL-2 proteins and STING machinery. Moreover,
149 during infection BAX can interact with IRF3, impacting STING signalling and
150 inflammation [51–53]. In addition, MAVS (mitochondrial antiviral-signalling protein) and

151 the nucleotide-binding oligomerization domain-like receptor protein 3 (NLRP3),
152 responsible for inflammasome activation, interact at MERCS, suggesting that these
153 contact areas also play a role in innate immunity [54–56].

154 On the other hand, the BCL-2 interaction network and downstream cascades can be
155 influenced by MERCS-mediated lipid transport. Of note, the majority of mitochondrial
156 lipids, including phospholipids, sphingolipids, and cholesterol, are synthesized in the
157 ER and then transferred to the mitochondria via MERCS [57,58]. Despite their minor
158 presence at the mitochondria, sphingolipids (e.g. ceramide and sphingosine-1P) have
159 been reported to play a crucial role in fine-tuning the apoptotic machinery: ceramide is
160 frequently associated with promoting BAX/BAK-dependent apoptosis, while
161 sphingosine-1P is linked to cell survival (reviewed in [59]). Additionally, elevated levels
162 of cholesterol at the mitochondria are correlated to impaired BAX activation and cell
163 survival [58,60]. In addition, cardiolipin (CL) plays a key role during apoptosis in the
164 mitochondrial targeting of BAX [61], its oligomerization [62], and the apoptotic pore
165 formation [63]. Importantly, CL (which is essential for mitochondrial cristae
166 maintenance) represents around 4-8% of the MOM lipids, but is highly enriched at
167 MERCS with 25% of the total lipid content [64], highlighting the importance of these
168 structures for BAX activation and the apoptotic pore formation.

169 In addition, BCL-2 family proteins are known to regulate essential MERCS-associated
170 activities such as Ca^{2+} signalling, mitochondrial dynamics, bioenergetics, the unfolded
171 protein response (UPR), mitochondrial quality control and autophagy (reviewed in
172 [34,65]). For example, the antiapoptotic protein BCL-2 and proapoptotic BOK, interact
173 with the MERCS-tether IP3R, displaying opposing roles in Ca^{2+} regulation, as both the
174 upregulation of BCL-2 and low levels of BOK are linked to limited Ca^{2+} fluxes to the
175 mitochondria [66,67]. Other studies support the idea that BOK interacts with IP3R at
176 MERCS modulates primarily mitochondrial dynamics and bioenergetics [68].
177 Antiapoptotic members such as BCL-XL, MCL-1 and BCL-B are also reported to bind
178 to IP3R limiting Ca^{2+} transport to the mitochondria [69–71]. Regarding the UPR,
179 several BCL-2 family proteins function as stress rheostats [72,73]. The BH3-only
180 proteins BID, PUMA, NOXA, BAD and BIM, are transcriptionally and post-
181 translationally induced under acute ER stress [74–77] and the apoptotic effector BOK
182 translocates to the mitochondria inducing MOMP [67,78,79]. BCL-2 family members
183 are also implicated in regulating mitochondrial dynamics, interacting with MFN2 and
184 the dynamin-related protein 1 (DRP1), affecting mitochondrial fusion and fission events
185 [80–82]. Finally, BCL-2 is reported to interact with Beclin-1 impairing autophagy [83].
186 Overall, independent studies report a continuous crosstalk between MERCS resident
187 proteins and BCL-2 family members which is responsible for fine-tuning their
188 respective activities and influencing cell fate. Alterations in the normal function of both
189 MERCS and BCL-2 family proteins are frequently associated with severe human
190 diseases. However, due to the dynamic nature of these structures and their
191 overlapping functions, it is complicated to discern whether alterations in MERCS are a
192 cause or a consequence of the disease. In the following sections, we will explore
193 variations in the composition of MERCS in relation to cancer, AD, and PD. These are
194 age-related diseases, in which alterations in MERCS, BCL-2 proteins, and
195 cGAS/STING-induced inflammation coexist, and so their interplay could play crucial
196 previously overlooked roles in disease.

197 **MERCS as a crucial axis in human disease**

198 MERCS and BCL-2 proteins in Cancer: Twisting homeostasis towards proliferation.

199 The communication between the ER and mitochondria plays a crucial role in cancer
200 development and progression. MERCS serve as signalling platforms that are involved
201 in rewiring normal cellular processes towards malignancy (**Figure 3A-B**). Aberrant
202 expression or mislocalization of MERCS-resident proteins is observed in several types
203 of cancer. For instance, the overexpression and increased MERCS localization of ER
204 stress sensors like ER oxidoreductin 1-alpha (ERO1- α) and RNA-dependent protein
205 kinase (PKR)-like ER kinase (PERK), are implicated in tumour initiation, progression,
206 and resistance to chemotherapy [84,85]. In breast cancer, the stress-activated
207 chaperone sigma-1 receptor (Sig1R) exhibits higher expression and increased
208 MERCS localization in metastatic cancer cells compared to normal tissues, modifying
209 IP3R-mediated Ca^{2+} dynamics and promoting cell invasiveness and migration [86–88].
210 Conversely, reduced expression of the MERCS-tether *MFN2* is correlated with worse
211 prognosis in colon and renal cancer subtypes [81,89], which taken together highlight
212 an overarching role for MERCS in cancer.

213 Regarding BCL-2 family proteins, the reduced apoptosis, excessive proliferation and
214 tumour chemotherapy resistance observed in cancer, are certainly linked to altered
215 signal crosstalk between the ER and the mitochondria [90,91]. For example, the
216 upregulation of antiapoptotic BCL-2 and BCL-XL is correlated with a reduction in IP3R-
217 mediated Ca^{2+} signalling and reduced cell death in several cancer types [66,92,93].
218 Proapoptotic BOK also reported to interact with the IP3R, is deleted across several
219 cancer types and associated with impaired cell death [94]. On the other hand,
220 mitochondrial lipid composition, fine-tuned by mitochondria-ER communication, is also
221 altered in cancer conditions. For example, elevated cholesterol levels at the
222 mitochondria are linked to reduced activation of the proapoptotic BCL-2 member BAX
223 and cell survival in cancer [60,95]. Moreover, dysregulation of CL and ceramide
224 metabolism, key lipids in promoting BAX/BAK activation and mitochondrial apoptosis
225 has been observed in several types of cancer (reviewed in [96,97]).

226 Finally, BAX/BAK-mediated cGAS/STING-regulated immune responses can impact
227 most of the aspects associated with tumorigenesis, from malignant cell transformation
228 to metastasis (reviewed in [98]). In this regard, BAX/BAK induced minority MOMP with
229 partial activation of the apoptotic machinery has been linked to the generation of
230 genomic instability, causing a cell death resistance phenotype that includes
231 colonization and metastasis *in vivo* [99], and drives aggressive features in residual
232 cancer cells [100]. On the other hand, sublethal BAX/BAK-dependent cGAS/STING
233 signalling activation can induce a chronic senescence-associated secretory phenotype
234 (SASP) [101]. Although originally believed to halt cancer progression due to their
235 characteristic growth arrest, senescent cells remain metabolically active and secrete
236 different inflammatory agents, generating a microenvironment that can promote tumour
237 growth [102].

238 An imbalance in MERCS-mediated functions and BCL-2 family proteins can therefore
239 lead to a plethora of cancer-driving processes, both within cells and in their
240 surroundings, including tumour initiation, progression, survival, and metastasis. This

241 underscores the importance of maintaining MERCS homeostasis to putatively predict
242 and prevent cancer-related features.

243

244 MERCS, BCL-2 proteins and Alzheimer's Disease: Proximity fails to reveal the whole
245 picture.

246 Alzheimer's Disease (AD) is the most prevalent neurodegenerative disorder worldwide,
247 leading to cognitive deficits and dementia [103]. Central to AD diagnosis is the
248 formation of intracellular neurofibrillary tangles composed of hyperphosphorylated tau
249 and extracellular plaques consisting of amyloid- β ($A\beta$) peptides [103]. These
250 aggregates and the subsequent inflammatory process are thought to lead to neuronal
251 dysfunction and loss. The γ -secretase complex, comprising presenilin 1 (PS1) or
252 presenilin 2 (PS2) as catalytic subunits, plays a crucial role in the cleavage of amyloid
253 precursor protein (APP), yielding $A\beta$ fragments. Importantly, both APP and the γ -
254 secretase complex have been identified at MERCS *in vitro*, suggesting a potential
255 involvement of MERCS in AD pathogenesis [104–107] (**Figure 3C**).

256 Mutant forms of APP, PS1 and PS2 enhance ER–mitochondrial tethering, affecting
257 Ca^{2+} dynamics and lipid metabolism, contributing to mitochondrial dysfunction and
258 neuronal cell death which are observed during AD [108–110]. For example, mutants of
259 PS2 modulate Ca^{2+} transfer to the mitochondria through interaction with MFN2 [108].
260 Studies in MEF cells lacking MFN2, showed diminished MERCS and reduced
261 interorganellar cholesterol trafficking [110]. However, in apparent contradiction to its
262 putative tethering function, knocking down MFN2 has also been associated with an
263 increase in mitochondria-ER contacts, altered mitochondrial Ca^{2+} transfer and reduced
264 APP processing [111]. Similar discrepancies exist regarding the putative role that $A\beta$
265 exerts over MERCS. *In vivo* studies in hippocampal neurons from AD rat models
266 indicate a reduction in MERCS upon $A\beta$ exposure, associated with diminished lipid
267 metabolism and alterations in the mitochondrial lipidome [112]. In accordance with this
268 finding, in *Drosophila* models, forced expression of an artificial linker that enhances
269 MERCS *in vivo* rescues locomotion and prolongs the survival in AD models [113].
270 However, other studies in primary hippocampal neurons show that $A\beta$ treatment
271 increases MERCS and disrupts Ca^{2+} homeostasis [114]. This was also the case in
272 fibroblasts from both familial and sporadic AD patients that showed an increase in ER-
273 mitochondria tethering with MERCS dysfunction, including alterations in phospholipid
274 and cholesterol metabolism [110]. While some of these opposing results are difficult to
275 interpret, they are perhaps not entirely unexpected as MERCS are mostly dynamic and
276 plastic cell signalling structures and as such will highly depend on the studied model
277 and disease snapshot. Importantly, studies in AD models have shown changes in the
278 MERCS proteome preceding the onset of cognitive symptoms, indicating a potential
279 role of MERCS dysregulation in driving disease progression [115], and underscoring
280 their role in AD.

281 At MERCS, antiapoptotic BCL-2 plays a crucial role in Ca^{2+} homeostasis and cell
282 survival, and its downregulation is associated with AD [116]. Reduced expression
283 levels of other antiapoptotic proteins such as BCL-XL, and MCL1, alongside elevated
284 levels of proapoptotic proteins like BIM or BAX, tilting the BCL-2 interaction network
285 towards death, is also associated with AD and the neuronal death observed during

286 disease progression [117] (and reviewed in [116]). Finally, recent findings indicate that
287 activation of the innate immune cGAS-STING pathway contributes to AD in 5×FAD
288 mice [118]. In this study, cGAS KO mice were significantly protected from cognitive
289 impairment, amyloid-β pathology, neuroinflammation, and other aspects associated
290 with AD [118]. Whilst the specific impact of BCL-2 proteins on the cGAS-STING
291 pathway related to AD pathogenesis remains poorly described, recent evidence linked
292 AD risk alleles with BAX-dependent mtDNA release and elevated microglial cGAS
293 pathway activation [119], which again points towards an interplay between MERCS
294 and apoptotic machinery proteins in AD. Non-cell autonomous effects downstream of
295 MERCS dysregulation may be particularly important in AD given its strong glial and
296 peripheral components.

297

298 MERCS and BCL-2 in Parkinson's Disease: Mitophagy to the rescue

299 Parkinson's Disease (PD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder characterized
300 by the loss of neurons, particularly in the *substantia nigra pars compacta* (SNpc),
301 leading to symptoms such as tremors, dyskinesia and dementia [120]. The disruption
302 of MERCS is associated with PD pathogenesis, thereby affecting the communication
303 between mitochondria and the ER (**Figure 3D**). Indeed, α-Synuclein, a protein which
304 is able to aggregate and is found in Lewy bodies, which are a hallmark of PD, is
305 localized at MERCS and implicated in their malfunction [121]. Wildtype α-Synuclein as
306 well as its PD-associated mutants A30P and A53T are shown to target MERCS through
307 the interaction with the VAPB/PTPIP51 tether-complex, and yet the impact of the
308 different mutations remains under investigation [122,123]. Nonetheless, the
309 impairment of VAPB and PTPIP51 tethering activity is associated with neuronal
310 synaptic dysfunction [124]. Furthermore, genetic mutations associated with familial PD
311 such as those in DJ-1, PINK1, and Parkin, proteins that are located at MERCS
312 [18,82,125]. Mutations in DJ-1 impair its role in maintaining Ca²⁺ homeostasis and
313 facilitating ER-mitochondrial tethering, altering the IP3R-GRP75-DJ1-VDAC complex
314 [17,18]. Importantly, ablation of DJ-1 increases mitochondria-ER distance, thereby
315 reducing mitochondria-ER communication, which can be rescued by wild-type DJ-1
316 but not by PD-related mutants [17,18]. In addition, mutations in the mitophagy
317 mediators PINK1 and Parkin, as well as in their associated proteins MIRO1 and MFN2,
318 are also related to MERCS dysregulation in PD [82,126–128]. Parkin expression
319 increases MERCS in HeLa cells, thereby enhancing Ca²⁺ signalling and ATP
320 production [126] and conversely, loss of Parkin in human fibroblasts leads to a
321 decrease in MERCS [82]. In Parkin KO mice and patients with Parkin mutations, the
322 absence of Parkin, however, was linked to increased connectivity between
323 mitochondria and the ER along with increased Ca²⁺ transport [127]. Mutations in
324 MIRO1 are associated with decreased MERCS and impaired Ca²⁺ transport to the
325 mitochondria in PD patients [128]. Furthermore, the MERCS tether MFN2 gets
326 phospho-ubiquitinated in Parkin/Pink1 dependent mitophagy. Mutations that inhibit
327 this posttranslational modification are reported to decrease MERCS, suggesting loss
328 of Parkin or ubiquitination-preventing mutations in MFN2, reduced MERCS and
329 mitophagy [82]. Importantly, recent studies have underscored the importance of
330 mitophagy in mitigating cytosolic mtDNA-dependent activation of cGAS/STING
331 inflammation during aging signalling [129], a pathway implicated in accelerating

332 neurodegeneration progression in a mouse model of PD [130]. As previously
333 mentioned, while the association between MERCS and PD is irrefutable, contradictory
334 findings could be explained by the dynamic and transient nature of MERCS associated
335 signalling, which highlights the need to carefully interpret these findings. This is
336 especially relevant for PD, which is tightly associated with mitochondrial malfunction,
337 through both genetics and toxic exposure to compounds such as rotenone.

338 BCL-2 proteins contribute to defects in mitophagy, neuronal cell death and the
339 pathogenesis of PD (reviewed in [131]). Although the precise molecular mechanisms
340 remains debated for PD, BCL-2 has been associated with MERCS localised
341 PINK1/Parkin and Beclin-1 to mediate autophagy [125,131]. Expression levels of BCL-
342 2 as well as other antiapoptotic proteins such as BCLXL are significantly decreased in
343 PD patients, with a negative correlation observed with disease duration and severity
344 [132,133]. Consistently, accumulation of the proapoptotic BAX has been observed in
345 neurons of the SNpc in post-mortem brains from PD patients [134], and in neurons
346 containing Lewy bodies [135]. Despite the specific impact of BCL-2 family proteins
347 directly activating cGAS-STING pathway and subsequent inflammation, this has not
348 yet been described in PD; their role in mitophagy could play an important role by
349 silencing this pathway [129,131]. Indeed, restoring autophagy through modulation of
350 BCL-2, has been already proposed for PD treatment [136].

351 **Concluding Remarks**

352 There is a clear link between alterations in MERCS and important human pathologies.
353 Here, we discuss cancer, PD, and AD, which are becoming increasingly prevalent in
354 our society. Enriched with stimuli-specific proteins and lipids, MERCS play a vital role
355 in various cellular functions such as Ca²⁺ signalling, lipid transfer, ROS production and
356 mitophagy under healthy conditions. This complexity poses a challenge in discerning
357 whether their dysregulation is a potential cause or a consequence of the disease.
358 However, some studies already suggest MERCS dynamics and composition preceding
359 the onset of cognitive symptoms, indicating a potential role of MERCS dysregulation
360 in driving disease progression. Therefore, designing molecules that improve
361 mitochondria-ER communication could lead to new therapeutic opportunities. Despite
362 their fundamental importance, there is significant controversy surrounding the
363 composition of MERCS. This is likely due to technical challenges associated with
364 studying these dynamic structures *in vivo*, the use of different experimental models,
365 and the low temporal resolution during their characterization. Some disease
366 developments may take years or even decades to manifest, suggesting that analysing
367 MERCS at a single time point may be insufficient and that some of the observations
368 could be an epiphenomenon. Understanding the sequence of events would provide
369 not only mechanistic details but could also provide a broader window for treatment.

370 BCL-2 family proteins, the main regulators of mitochondrial apoptosis, are responsible
371 for several MERCS-related functions and they are also associated with the imbalance
372 in apoptotic cell death observed in cancer, PD, and AD. Recently, the mitochondrial
373 apoptotic machinery has been associated to the release of mtDNA and the activation
374 of the cGAS/STING pathway. As this signalling requires mitochondria-ER
375 communication, it suggests that MERCS could orchestrate or sense this pathway prior
376 to its effect at the cell or organism level. Connected to this, sublethal activation of the

377 apoptotic machinery can lead to genomic instability and has been associated with a
378 pro-oncogenic outcome, but could also play a role in the neuronal reprogramming that
379 occurs during neurodegeneration. Of note, sub-lethal apoptotic stress has been barely
380 explored in neurodegeneration, and considering that BCL-2 proteins are involved in
381 neuropathies, that these diseases have described cGAS/STING pathway activation
382 and that cellular senescence is a hallmark in these pathologies, it is highly possible
383 that the apoptotic machinery mediates the inflammation observed in
384 neurodegenerative diseases, contributing to MERCS dysregulation and the disease
385 onset. Therefore, striving to investigate these novel aspects of the BCL-2 protein
386 family, moving away from their canonical roles in apoptosis, is key, and therapeutically
387 targeting MERCS alongside the apoptotic machinery could be crucial in addressing
388 neurodegeneration. This approach not only offers the potential to prevent neuronal
389 death but could also mitigate the associated inflammatory signalling and cellular
390 senescence, thereby ameliorating neuronal health and addressing these pathologies.

391 In summary, MERCS are important underexplored structures which, together with
392 apoptotic machinery (e.g., BCL-2 family proteins), play crucial physiological roles
393 maintaining cellular homeostasis. Alterations in these structures are linked to
394 pathologies such as cancer, PD and AD, affecting critical cellular functions like Ca^{2+}
395 signalling or mitophagy. The dysregulation of MERCS could even drive disease
396 progression, with recent evidence suggesting a novel role for them in
397 neurodegeneration by activating inflammatory pathways such as cGAS/STING, and
398 contributing to genomic instability. Therefore, therapeutic strategies targeting MERCS
399 and BCL-2 family proteins could offer new approaches to treat these diseases.

400 **Conflicts of Interest**

401 The author declares no competing interests.

402

403 **Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process**

404 During the preparation of this work the author used chatGPT to check for grammar.
405 After using this tool/service, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and
406 takes full responsibility for the content of the publication.

407

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417

418 **Figure legends:**

419 **Figure1. Schematic representation of MERCS composition and functional**
420 **tethers. I)** IP3R-GRP75-DJ1-VDAC axes represent the main Ca²⁺ regulator from the
421 Endoplasmic-Reticulum (ER) to the mitochondria. Ca²⁺ from the ER reaches the
422 mitochondria outer membrane (MOM) via the interaction of IP3R with VDAC and is
423 positively regulated by GRP75 and DJ-1, forming a tetrameric structure. This complex
424 is also modulated by Sig1-R, which accumulates at MERCS, stabilizing IP3R at
425 MERCS. Moreover, TG2 binds to the complex, favouring Ca²⁺-transport to the
426 mitochondrial matrix passing the mitochondrial inner membrane (MIM) using the MCU.
427 **II)** BAP31 targeted to the ER interacts with TOMM40 and Fis1 at the MOM and is
428 regulated by PACS2 (Phosphofurin Acidic Cluster Sorting Protein 2), to promote
429 mitochondria-ER communication. **III)** VAPB in the ER membrane interacts with
430 PTPIP51 (P-51) at the MOM, and directly regulates MERCS distance and surface of
431 contact, acting as a physical tether. **IV)** PDZD8 is an ERMES like protein found in
432 mammals, located at the ER with the capacity to enhance mitochondria-ER contacts.
433 The existence of a binding partner of PDZD8 at the MOM remains undefined, marked
434 by a question mark (?). **V)** MFN2 is located both at the ER and the MOM and so is able
435 to bridge these two organelles. The role of MFN2 as a MERCS tether is still debated
436 and is represented here with a question mark (?). MERCS are also responsible for lipid
437 exchange between the ER and the mitochondria. Abbreviations: Phosphatidylserine
438 (PS), Phosphatidylethanolamine (PE), IP3R (Inositol 1,4,5-trisphosphate receptor),
439 GRP75 (Glucose-Regulated Protein 75), VDAC (Voltage-Dependent Anion Channel),
440 Sig1-R (Sigma-1 receptor), TG2 (Transglutaminase 2), BAP31 (B-cell receptor-
441 associated protein 31), TOMM40 (Translocase of outer mitochondrial membrane 40),

442 Fis1 (Fission 1 protein), VAPB (VAMP-associated protein B), P-51 (Protein-tyrosine
443 phosphatase-interacting protein-51), PDZD8 (PDZ domain-containing protein 8),
444 MFN2 (Mitofusin 2). Figure was created using Biorender.

445 **Figure 2. The BCL-2 family machinery at the crossroad between apoptosis,**
446 **genomic instability and inflammation.** Cellular stress, including stress originated at
447 the ER, converge at the mitochondria during (sub)lethal apoptotic stress. The
448 canonical apoptotic effectors BAX and BAK are activated either through direct
449 interaction with BH3-only proteins (e.g., BID) or indirectly by release from antiapoptotic
450 members (BCL-2/BCL-XL/MCL-1). Upon activation, BAX/BAK undergo a profound
451 structural rearrangement and oligomerize to form apoptotic pores, allowing the release
452 of mitochondrial content to the cytosol. Depending on the magnitude and the durability
453 of the stress, this results in three different outcomes: apoptotic cell death (left), non-
454 lethal inflammatory signalling that includes genomic instability (middle), and
455 inflammation (right). Above a lethal threshold, apoptogenic factors (e.g. Cytochrome-c
456 or SMAC) induce apoptosome formation and caspase activation for apoptotic cell
457 dismissal. In the context of non-lethal permeabilization, partial release of cytochrome-
458 c with subsequent sublethal caspase activation can trigger DNA damage and
459 prooncogenic genomic instability. Finally, a proinflammatory outcome occurs when i)
460 released SMAC induces NF- κ B pathway activation via RIP1 and RIP3, ii) released
461 mtRNA activates MAVS, RIG-1 and MDA5 for TBK1 activation and subsequent
462 interleukin production, and iii) released mtDNA is recognised by cGAS to produce
463 cGAMP, which subsequently, induces STING activation at the ER. STING
464 translocation to the Golgi induces TBK1/IRF3 activation (phosphorylation) and
465 interleukin production (e.g. interferon type-1, IL-6 and others). Abbreviations: NF- κ B
466 (Nuclear Factor Kappa-Light-Chain-Enhancer of Activated B Cells), RIP1/3 (Receptor-
467 Interacting Serine/Threonine-Protein-Kinase 1/3), MAVS (Mitochondrial Antiviral-
468 Signalling Protein), RIG-1 (Retinoic Acid-Inducible Gene 1), MDA5 (Melanoma
469 Differentiation-Associated Protein-5), TBK1 (TANK-Binding Kinase-1), cGAS (Cyclic
470 GMP-AMP Synthase), STING (Stimulator of Interferon Genes). Figure was created
471 using Biorender.

472

473 **Figure 3. MERCS composition under healthy and disease conditions. A)** Under
474 healthy conditions BCL-2 retrotranslocates BAX-type proteins from the mitochondria
475 to the cytosol, and transiently interacts with the IP3R receptor to modulate Ca^{2+} fluxes
476 to the mitochondria. APP is processed into A β 40 and A β 42 by gamma-secretase, the
477 catalytical subunits of which are PS1 and the PS2. α Synuclein binds to the MERCS
478 tether VAPB-PTPIP51 modulating its function. Mitochondria undergo fusion and fission
479 events, where MIRO1 plays a role, to adapt mitochondrial dynamics to cellular
480 requirements. Damaged mitochondria undergo mitophagy using the parkin/PINK1
481 machinery. Finally, constant lipid exchange between ER and the mitochondria occurs
482 at MERCS. **B)** A hallmark of cancer cells is increased levels of the antiapoptotic BCL-
483 2 family members (e.g. BCL-2, BCL-XL or MCL-1) and a decrease in the proapoptotic
484 members (e.g. BAX, BAK, BOK and others). BCL-2 and BCL-XL can reduce the IP3R-
485 mediated Ca^{2+} transfer to the mitochondria, reducing cell death, but also affecting Ca^{2+}
486 metabolism required for cell proliferation. Ca^{2+} fluxes are also regulated in certain
487 cancer types by the overexpression of Sig-1R that favours cell migration and

488 proliferation. ERO-1 α is a stress sensor protein located at MERCs and its
489 overexpression is associated with cancer malignancy. Also, low expression levels of
490 MFN2 are associated with worse prognosis in cancer. Finally, MERCs-mediated lipid
491 transfer favours cholesterol (CHOL) trafficking to the mitochondria, limiting apoptotic
492 cell death. **C)** In AD APP processing into A β 42 is increased. High expression levels of
493 A β 42 are associated with changes in MERCs and their associated functions. Mutant
494 forms of APP, PS1 and PS2 are shown to enhance MERCs tethering, altering Ca²⁺
495 dynamics and lipid metabolism. PS1 and PS2 are also differentially associated with
496 MFN2 during AD. Mutations in APP, PS1 and PS2 are associated with AD and depicted
497 here with yellow spheres. BCL-2 protein levels appear to be altered in AD, and usually
498 correlate with decreased levels of the antiapoptotic members BCL-2, BCL-XL and
499 others) and increased proapoptotic members (here the BH3 only protein BIM is
500 illustrated). These conditions promote BAX/BAK activation for the apoptotic pore
501 formation, allowing mitochondrial content release e.g. apoptogenic factors and mtDNA.
502 The apoptotic pore has a protein-lipid nature, being enriched in lipids like cardiolipin.
503 **D)** In PD there is an augmented level of α Synuclein, whose activity at MERCs is
504 associated with alterations in Ca²⁺ signalling via IP3R and in MERCs-tethering via the
505 interaction with VAPB-PIIP51. Mutations in α Synuclein, DJ-1, Miro-1, Parkin and
506 PINK1 are associated to PD and depicted here with yellow spheres. Defects in
507 mitophagy are also associated with mitochondrial malfunction and enhanced
508 BAX/BAK-dependent cell death. **A-D**, mechanistic details about some of these features
509 are poorly defined and here represented with question marks. Figure was created
510 using Biorender.

511

512

513 **Glossary Box**

514 **Apoptotic cell death:** Apoptosis is a form of programmed cell death characterized by
515 distinct morphological changes such as cell shrinkage, nuclear fragmentation, and
516 formation of apoptotic bodies. This process plays a crucial role in maintaining tissue
517 homeostasis by eliminating unwanted or damaged cells.

518 **Autophagy:** Autophagy is a cellular process in which cells degrade and recycle their
519 own components, including organelles and proteins, to maintain cellular homeostasis
520 and remove damaged or unnecessary material. It plays a vital role in cellular health
521 and adaptation to stress conditions.

522 **BCL-2 family:** The BCL-2 protein family comprises proteins that play a crucial role in
523 determining the fate of cells by regulating apoptosis. These proteins have been
524 classically described to control the permeability of the mitochondrial membrane,
525 influencing cell fate and its physiological outcomes.

526 **Calcium (Ca²⁺) signalling:** Ca²⁺ signaling refers to the process of connecting
527 dynamic, temporal changes in intracellular calcium levels across different cellular
528 compartments orchestrated by calcium-dependent sensors and effectors.

529 **cGAS/STING pathway:** The cGAS/STING pathway is a cellular signalling cascade
530 that detects DNA in the cytoplasm, initiating immune responses against pathogens or

531 damaged/stressed cells. It begins with the enzyme cyclic GMP-AMP synthase (cGAS)
532 recognizing foreign or abnormal DNA and ends with the activation of the stimulator of
533 interferon genes (STING), leading to the production of type I interferons and other
534 cytokines.

535 **ERMES complex:** The ERMES (Endoplasmic Reticulum–Mitochondria Encounter
536 Structure) complex is a molecular structure found at the interface between the ER and
537 mitochondria in eukaryotic cells. It facilitates communication and exchange of lipids
538 and proteins between these two organelles, playing a crucial role in maintaining cellular
539 homeostasis and function.

540 **MERCS:** MERCS, short for Mitochondria-ER Contact Sites, are specialized regions
541 within cells where mitochondria and the ER closely interact. These sites, also known
542 as MAMs (Mitochondria-Associated ER Membranes), facilitate crucial cellular
543 processes such as calcium signalling, lipid metabolism, and autophagy by enabling the
544 exchange of ions, lipids, and other signalling molecules between the two organelles.

545 **MERCS-tether:** refers to the protein complexes that physically link mitochondria and
546 the ER at MERCS. These tethering proteins play a critical role in maintaining the
547 structural integrity of MERCS and facilitating the exchange of molecules between
548 organelles.

549 **Minority MOMP:** Minority MOMP describes a process in which only a fraction of
550 mitochondria within a cell undergo permeabilization, leading to the activation of
551 sublethal caspase activity. In contrast to complete MOMP, which results in caspase
552 activation surpassing a given threshold and subsequent apoptotic cell death, minority
553 MOMP with partial caspase activation, may lead to genomic instability of the survivor
554 cells. This instability potentially contributes to tumorigenesis or other pathological
555 conditions.

556 **Mitochondrial quality control:** Mitochondrial quality control refers to the collective
557 processes by which cells maintain healthy and functional mitochondria. This includes
558 mechanisms such as mitochondrial biogenesis, fusion and fission dynamics,
559 mitophagy and the unfolded protein response.

560 **Senescence:** Cellular senescence refers to a state in which cells cease to divide and
561 undergo irreversible growth arrest in response to various stresses or signals, such as
562 DNA damage or telomere shortening. Senescent cells typically display altered gene
563 expression patterns and may secrete pro-inflammatory molecules, contributing to
564 tissue aging and age-related diseases.

565

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870 **Figure 1.**

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873 **Figure 2.**

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877 **Figure 3.**

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880 **Highlights**

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882 - MERCs serve as signaling hubs involved in vital cellular processes such as calcium
883 signaling, lipid metabolism, autophagy, and apoptosis.

884 - Alterations in MERCs dynamics and composition are closely associated with severe
885 human diseases such as neurodegenerative disorders and cancer.

886 - The BCL-2 protein family, primary regulators of mitochondrial apoptosis and key
887 players in maintaining cellular homeostasis, operate at MERCs to fulfill essential
888 cellular functions.

889 - Apoptotic machinery-induced cGAS-STING pathway activation and proinflammatory
890 signaling, requires mitochondria-ER communication and is affected in cancer, AD and
891 PD.

892

893 **Outstanding questions**

894 - Is the composition of MERCS tailored to specific tissues or cell-types, adapting to
895 specific needs? Do different MERCS tethers work simultaneously? Do they compete
896 for the same locations? Can they exhibit redundancy? What is their conformational
897 status when they are not bridging interorganellar connections?

898 - Are changes in the structure or function of MERCS a potential cause of disease, a
899 result of disease, or are they adaptive adjustments to compensate cellular imbalances
900 during disease development? Do those changes remain constant throughout the entire
901 process? Could restoring MERCS function effectively ameliorate disease progression?

902 - Can correlations be established between disruptions in MERCS-resident proteins and
903 diseases, potentially leading to their use as diagnostic biomarkers? Could the
904 interactions between BCL-2 family proteins and MERCS functions be leveraged to
905 assess overall cellular health or susceptibility to disease?

906 - Is the activation of sublethal apoptotic machinery causing chronic inflammation and
907 cellular stress, contributing to the excessive accumulation of A β or α -synuclein
908 observed in AD and PD or a consequence of these pathologies? Would inhibiting low-
909 level inflammation reduce the protein aggregation and disease progression?

910 - Considering the role of MERCS in transferring signals to mitochondria and modifying
911 mitochondrial membranes, are they responsible for the selective content release from
912 the apoptotic pores? Do MERCS directly mediate mtDNA release and pro-
913 inflammatory signalling upon apoptotic machinery activation?

914 - Could targeting the non-canonical roles of BCL-2 proteins in MERCS dynamics and
915 apoptotic signaling unlock groundbreaking therapies for halting or even reversing
916 neurodegenerative diseases like Parkinson's and Alzheimer's?

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